

THE SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF ANTHROPONYMS IN IDIOMS AND PROVERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Rahimova Dilnura

Master's student

Department of English language and literature

National University of Uzbekistan

dilnushrahimova04@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19387938>

Key words: *anthroponyms, proverbs, idioms, cultural values.*

This paper examines proverbs and idioms with personal names in English and Uzbek. These anthroponymic units reflect human traits, social values, and cultural traditions, shaped by historical and religious contexts. While relatively rare, they share common features across both languages. Analyzing them provides insight into societal worldviews and highlights the potential for a bilingual dictionary of anthroponymic proverbs for comparative linguistic research.

Phraseological units are characterized by a literal relationship between their ways of expression and content, which reflects the dialectical unity of structural and semantic aspects. Similar to words that carry lexical meaning, phraseological units function as stable linguistic units with their own phraseological meanings. The semantic nature of phraseological units is deeply rooted in the encyclopedic knowledge of a particular nation, including its historical background, cultural traditions, literary heritage, folklore, religious beliefs, and customs. Among the various components of phraseological units, onomastic elements, particularly anthroponyms, play a significant role in representing national cultural identity. These elements influence the etymology, formation, and metaphorical interpretation of phraseology units. However, phraseological units containing anthroponymic components in unrelated languages such as English and Uzbek remain insufficiently explored semantic studies. This research aims to analyze and classify such phraseological units in order to reveal their associative meanings related to human characteristics.

A proverb is a short and widely used traditional expression that conveys general truth and shared beliefs derived from common human experience [1]. According to Merriam-Webster dictionary anthroponym is "a person's name," typically a proper name used to identify a human being. This term is formed from the Greek elements anthrop- ("human") and -onym ("name") [2]. An anthroponym, especially a personal name, is distinguished from many other names that have the peculiarity of the individualization of an object: each object of the nomination (person) has a name. The Namespace is limited. Personal names are repeated, which makes it possible to give an additional name. In a developed society, the official name of a person has the formula of his name: a certain procedure for following anthroponyms and common names (ethnonyms, specialties, professions, titles, etc.) [3]. The presence of personal names in phraseological expressions often symbolizes human characteristics, social behavior, and moral qualities. Therefore, the semantic analysis of anthroponyms in idioms and proverbs provides valuable insight into the national worldview of English and Uzbek linguistic communities.

In this article, a couple of research methods are used to explore the linguocultural analysis of phraseological units that contain anthroponymic components in both English and Uzbek. It mainly focuses on understanding how language and culture interact with each other. Semantic

analysis has been employed to examine the specific semantic features of phraseological units. This approach considers these units as integrated structures in which meaning is formed through the interaction between linguistic expression associated with personal names. English proverbs often contain personal names, and many of these names are connected to historical personalities or biblical characters. Such names add cultural depth and background meaning to the proverb. For instance, Jack of all trades, master of none (a person who has many skills but is not truly expert in any of them). As old as Methuselah, (referring to extreme old age, based on biblical figure) [4]. In English, the proverb "Simple Simon met a pieman" uses the name Simon to symbolize a naïve or foolish individual, highlighting qualities such as simplicity, innocence, or lack of cleverness. Similarly, the expression "Every Tom, Dick and Harry" employs common English male names to refer to ordinary people in general, stressing the idea of typicality or universality rather than any specific individual. When it comes to proverbs with religious references, "Doubting Thomas" can be given as an example. It refers to the biblical apostle who doubted Jesus' resurrection, representing skepticism [5]. When it comes to anthroponymic proverbs in Uzbek, they contain personal names, and many of these are rooted in the nation's historical heritage, cultural values, and Islamic traditions. These anthroponyms reflect the collective memory and spiritual background of the Uzbek people, enriching the proverbs with deeper cultural and symbolic meaning. For instance, in Uzbek, the proverb "Alining o'ligi-Botirning tirigidan yaxshi" conveys the idea that even the memory of a truly brave and honorable person is more valuable than the life of someone who lacks courage or purpose. In other words, it suggests that genuine heroism and dignity outweigh a meaningless or unworthy existence. Furthermore, "Ermat boy bo'lsa, el boqar, Qorammat boy bo'lsa, yol boqar" refers to the original contrast between generosity-Ermat and selfishness-Qorammat by using simpler explanatory language. Another example can be "Hasan aka quysin, Qo'chqor aka ichsin" reflects true friendship, in which friends share everything and remain faithful to each other, with Hasan and Qo'chqor representing the ideal of loyal companionship [6].

Proverbs featuring personal names are not that common in speech and writing. Nonetheless, anthroponymic proverbs in English and Uzbek share common traits, using names to represent broader social values. They include both current and archaic expressions, with cultural, religious and historical factors shaping their usage in each language. In order to be aware of comparison of English and Uzbek proverbs including anthroponyms, it is offered to create a special dictionary which contains those types of proverbs in both English and Uzbek languages. Studying these proverbs offers insights into the worldviews and traditions of English and Uzbek speakers.

References:

1. <https://www.britannica.com/art/proverb>
2. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/anthroponym?utm>
3. Koziyeva I. K. Anthroponymy studies // International scientific journal. – 2023. – Vol. 2, iss. 10.
4. Ray J. A complete collection of English proverbs. – London: Forgotten Books, 2013. – 319 p.
5. Contrastive study of proverbs with anthroponymic components in English and Uzbek languages // The Light of Civilization. – 2025.

6. O'zbek xalq maqollari / Tuzuvchilar: T. Mirzayev, A. Musoqulov, B. Sarimsoqov. – Toshkent: Sharq, 2005. – 253 b.